

FORMATION OF STYLISTIC COMPETENCE AT A MILITARY INSTITUTE

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Abstract. The article focuses on the study of the process of developing stylistic competence among cadets at a military university. Stylistic competence is considered a key component of professional language training, ensuring the ability to appropriately use various functional styles depending on the communicative situation.

The paper analyzes the theoretical foundations of stylistic competence, its role in professional military discourse, and the specifics of its development within a military educational institution. Particular attention is given to practical methods and approaches such as text analysis and editing, situational modeling, role-playing, and the integration of interdisciplinary and digital technologies. The methodological recommendations presented in the article are aimed at developing skills in working with texts in official and professional styles, thereby enhancing the quality of cadet preparation for future service.

Introduction

The modern English lesson must meet the demands placed on education by society as a whole. Foreign language communicative competence represents a complex unity of more narrowly focused competencies that ensure full-fledged communication

in a foreign language. Currently, there are several approaches to defining the concept of foreign language communicative competence (FLCC) and its component structure. Within the framework of English language instruction, the study of stylistics as a separate linguistic aspect is not formally provided, but mastering English as a means of communication is impossible without acquiring basic knowledge of the stylistic features of the language. These concepts, as well as the ability to choose language tools appropriate to the communication situation, taking into account the stylistic component, are formed in English lessons not only through the development of linguistic competence (i.e., knowledge of phonetic, lexical, grammatical, and orthographic norms) but also through the actualization of interdisciplinary connections.

Stylistic competence is developed throughout the entire English language learning process at school, as part of mastering all components of FLCC. A key role in the comparative analysis of similar linguistic phenomena is assigned to the teacher, whose main task is to draw parallels between the native and foreign languages and to convey the stylistic features of English to students.

Research Objective. The aim of this research is to develop and justify effective pedagogical approaches, methods, and tools aimed at cultivating cadets' ability to use various stylistic means and adapt their communicative behavior according to the communication situation in both professional and academic spheres of military discourse.

Main part. Stylistics is defined as a linguistic science that studies the functional varieties of language. The methods for developing stylistic competence are divided into general didactic and specialized approaches

Among the effective techniques, the following can be highlighted:

- stylistic analysis of words, forms, and constructions;
- working with texts (analysis, editing, transformation);
- role-playing and modeling of professional situations;
- creating texts in various styles followed by editing;

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- use of digital technologies (presentations, electronic lectures);
- use of authentic texts with a clearly expressed stylistic affiliation. [Soboleva & Kazantseva, 2020].

In linguistic literature, stylistics is defined as the study of styles—a linguistic science that describes the functional side of the language system in its modern state and diachrony, explaining the patterns of language use in speech. There are several methods and techniques that contribute to the development of stylistic competence. Depending on learning goals, these methods perform educational, developmental, and formative functions. There are two groups of teaching methods: a) general methods applicable to all academic subjects, described in didactics; b) subject-specific methods, which describe the process of teaching particular academic subjects [Soboleva & Kazantseva, 2020]. There are methods for teaching stylistic resources, stylistically differentiated speech, and methods of conveying stylistic knowledge. Examples include stylistic analysis of words, forms, and constructions (introduction to stylistic norms), discussions using dictionaries and reference materials, independent work identifying stylistic characteristics of language units, and stylistic and lexical analysis of texts or text fragments. Other effective techniques include constructing texts in various styles, revising or reconstructing student-created texts, using field-specific materials for discourse analysis, text editing and transformation, and independent production of texts in different styles.

Computer-based tools (multimedia, presentations, e-textbooks, online lectures) and project-based technologies are also recommended. Discourse analysis requires a combination of linguistic and related ethnographic, psychological, and sociological methodologies, including interviews, observation, and experimentation.

The text is not only the highest communicative unit but also a unit of discourse. As a speech unit, the text enables the study of language units in terms of their meaning, structure, and functioning, allowing for an understanding of essential linguistic features along with their functional potential. Therefore, a text should:

- be an original literary work or an unadapted scientific or journalistic piece with a

clear stylistic affiliation;

- be complete in content and structure;
- match educational objectives and a specific communicative task;
- be accessible, engaging, and problem-oriented;
- contribute to improving speech culture. [Slobodskaya,2011]

Depending on the nature of the literary text, a particular type of analysis is chosen. A complete literary text is best approached with comprehensive analysis, while a fragment can be analyzed at one linguistic level. Before analysis, students should identify the speech type, topic, and main idea of the text. Linguistic analysis fosters the ability to select expressive means according to the text's idea and topic, as lexical, morphological, and syntactic analysis shows how stylistic meaning is conveyed. Understanding a text's structure and content through linguistic analysis is essential for accurate reproduction. Students may use synonymous substitutions because they retain the content and authorial style of the original. Comparative analysis of the source and its summary is also effective. [Gumerova,2022]

Developing stylistic competence is a complex task closely tied to the formation of overall FLCC. For cadets, this requires an integrated approach that includes cognitive, practical, and communicative elements. Teaching different speech styles, analyzing and editing texts, situational modeling, and role-playing are key to developing stylistic competence.

The cognitive approach involves awareness of language style differentiation, familiarity with functional styles, their features, and roles in professional communication. Analyzing texts of different styles—e.g., official documents, scientific articles, reports—helps students distinguish between stylistically appropriate and inappropriate language. The practical and communicative approaches focus on applying style: stylistic editing of texts, role-playing, modeling professional situations, writing texts in different genres and styles, and modifying or improving texts to match style and register. [Jenner, 2023]

Examples include writing reports, memorandums, official notes, or using

sample-based writing tasks where cadets produce texts aligned with stylistic norms. Practice in real or simulated situations—briefings, reports, negotiations, or tasks requiring speech style adaptation—is effective in mastering the stylistic meanings of various language units and in learning to choose language tools appropriately based on the communicative goal.

Thus, the development of stylistic competence requires a comprehensive approach:

- Cognitive approach – awareness of stylistic differentiation, knowledge of functional styles and their functions;
- Practical approach – stylistic editing, production of texts in various genres, working with samples and models;

Communicative approach – participation in briefings, negotiations, preparation of reports, memoranda, and other forms of military communication. . [Burke& & Zerkowitz, 2014]

The teacher should draw cadets’ attention to both explicit and implicit stylistic elements in the language and encourage the use of a variety of linguistic registers.

Conclusion

The formation of stylistic competence plays a key role in cadet education as it ensures effective professional and interpersonal communication across various military contexts. Mastery of military discourse styles and genres supports the successful performance of professional tasks such as writing reports, delivering presentations, giving orders, and public speaking, all of which are essential for a military career. To effectively develop stylistic competence, diverse methods should be used, including text analysis, situational modeling, and role-playing. Assignments should also foster the ability to adapt style to various communicative situations. The use of authentic texts and situational tasks helps cadets better understand military discourse and adjust their communication style accordingly.

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Effective formation of stylistic competence requires the integration of knowledge from linguistics, pedagogy, and military-specific content, enabling deeper comprehension of communicative norms and stylistic features in military communication. It is also recommended to develop specialized teaching materials, conduct seminars and training for instructors, and regularly assess cadets' stylistic competence to refine the learning process. These conclusions emphasize the importance of a systematic and targeted approach to developing cadets' stylistic competence in the context of English language education at military institutions.

Stylistic competence is a crucial component in the training of cadets, ensuring effective professional and interpersonal communication within the framework of military discourse. Mastery of styles and genres contributes to successful professional performance.

To develop stylistic competence, it is necessary to:

- apply methods of analysis and modeling;
- design and implement situational tasks;
- create and utilize specialized teaching materials;
- conduct seminars and training sessions for instructors;
- regularly assess cadets' competence levels in order to adjust the educational process accordingly.

Thus, the development of stylistic competence requires a systematic approach that combines linguistic knowledge with military-specific content and should be viewed as a strategic objective of language education in a military university.

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